

TEXTILES MADE OF POPLAR FIBERS

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Abstract: Unfortunately, the textile industry is one of the most polluting industries in the world. Since fibers are the building blocks of textiles, it is important to use environmentally friendly and sustainable fibers to mitigate the pollution of the textile industry. In recent years, sustainable production methods of man-made fibers have received great interest, and a lot of investment has been made to increase the production of such fibers. For sure, these are very important efforts to create an environmentally friendly textile. However, using non-traditional natural fibers might be an alternative solution to mitigate the pollution generated by the textile industry. Poplar fibers are one of the non-traditional seed fibers that grow naturally, without requiring additional irrigation. However, these fibers are not harvested at industrial levels yet. Main reason for this is their short length, which makes them a difficult candidate for spinning. These fibers nevertheless have exceptional properties such as huge lumen, extra low density, very hydrophobic surface and superior insulation behavior. In our recently funded projects, it has been shown that poplar fibers can be turned into nonwoven samples through a wet laid process. In addition, they can be blended with other fibers to develop needle-punched nonwovens or carded and hot-pressed webs. These webs provide exceptional thermal and sound insulation, oil and dye absorption. Coating these webs with silver nanowires results in conductive webs which can be used for electronic textile applications. Developing traditional and advanced textiles using these nontraditional fibers is the aim of this study.

Keywords: sustainability, natural fibers, poplar fibers, electronic textiles

1 INTRODUCTION

Each natural fiber has unique properties and they have been extensively used in our daily lives. For thousands of years, cotton, flax, wool and silk had been the most consumed fibers owing to their various characteristic features. For all these fibers, the fiber length plays a critical role since it is the main requirement to spin a thread. Although there has been a growing interest in finding alternative fiber sources, spinnability remains a restricting factor for their applications.

Hollow plant fibers such as kapok, milkweed, and poplar are particularly notable for their light structure, insulation properties, and versatility in area of use, making them excellent candidates for oil-water separation, thermal insulation and sound sorption [1]. In this regard, poplar fiber remains an area of interest among these non-traditional fibers, although poplar trees, namely genus *Populus*, are widely distributed across the northern hemisphere, Turkey being a considerable habitat having poplars as a key species for industrial purposes in the central and eastern regions (Fig. 1a) [2,3]. They are known for their rapid growth, short lifespan, high-quality wood and fiber production, and ease of propagation. [2,3]. The seed fiber of these trees as depicted in Fig. 1b, is discarded as bio-waste or used as a filling medium.

Figure 1 Poplar tree (a) and poplar seed fibers (b)

Chemical composition of poplar seed fibers includes cellulose of 41%-44%, hemicellulose of 19%-21%, lignin of 29%, and extractive compounds (mostly wax) of 4%-9% [4]. In terms of appearance and morphology,

poplar fiber is comparable to kapok fiber, since poplars are characterized by their yellowish color, lightweight and fluffy nature owing to their wax coated surface and large hollow lumen [1,4,5]. The hollow fraction constitutes about 80-90 % of the fiber cross-section [5]. As a result of this major void in the fiber structure, the density of poplar fibers can be as low as 0.3 g/cm³ [4,6].

Figure 2 Longitudinal (a) and cross-section (b) SEM images of the poplar seed fibers, scale bars indicate 20 µm

The properties of these fibers differ according to the tree and place from which they are derived; nonetheless, these natural fibers are worth noticing based on their features including high degree of hollowness, hydrophobic surface characteristic, and low density.

2 APPLICATION OF POPLAR FIBERS

2.1 Conductive Interfaces

A preliminary study focusing on the versatile uses of poplar fibers includes their utilization in the form of conductive interfaces. Poplar fibers were hand-harvested and then cleaned manually. At this stage, the harvest was insufficient to form a fibrous surface using laboratory equipment. Therefore, a different approach was taken, in which non-woven pads were produced via spray coating a polymer solution on the fiber bundle [5,7]. These pads

were then coated with silver nanowires to impart electrical conductivity as seen in Fig.3.

Figure 3 Spandex solution spray coated poplar nonwoven pad (a) [AG 2019], conductive poplar pad (b,c)

Conductive poplar pads were employed as insoles in a smart shoe application to track mobility signals during the day as an endeavor in the Poplar Shoe project under WEARSUSTAIN program (Fig. 4). Another approach towards sustainable electronics was the production of flexible capacitors for wearable electronic applications [7].

Figure 4 Screen shots of a mobile app which is monitoring various data obtained from the conductive poplar pads employed in a smart shoe

2.2 Nonwovens for Oil Absorption, Sound Insulation and Thermal Applications

Poplar fiber has generally been examined in the forms of composite filler, film or fibers. Forming these fibers into nonwoven fabrics have been accomplished by mixing them with hollow PET fibers. [7]. These blends were firstly carded (Fig. 5a) and then mechanically bonded (Fig. 5b). Resulting nonwovens consisted of up to 37% of poplar fiber. The hollowness of the poplar fiber used in the study was reported to be 82%. The air retention capacity of these hollow fibers makes them effective materials that provide high thermal and sound insulation in comparison with widely exploited natural fibers like cotton, wool and hemp [5]. Similarly, it has been observed that poplar fibers are significantly higher than goose feather and wool in terms of fill power value, furthermore, poplar outperforms hollow polyester fibers in terms of thermal resistance than [1]. Knowing that poplar fibers have superior thermal insulation, the research interest has been shifted towards benefiting from them in an active manner. For this purpose, the usability of conductive poplar/PET blended fabrics in heated fabric applications becomes an area of interest. Poplar fibers exhibit inherent oleophilicity owing to their waxy surface, which make them promising and sustainable mediums for oil-water separation. In the study examining toluene and rose oil absorbency, it was shown that poplar fibers with a water

contact angle (WCA) of 125° could absorb oil more than 30 times their own weight [5]. Similarly, poplar blend nonwovens exhibited higher WCAs, rose oil absorption and methylene blue removal as the poplar fiber content increased the fabric structure [8].

Figure 5 Carded web (a) and needle-punched nonwoven (b)

2.3 Yarn Formation

Being a relatively short natural fiber, spinning of poplar fibers has remained as a challenge. Blending poplar having a fiber length of 3.29 mm with recycled PET fiber, yarn formation was achieved by Open-End spinning method. Yarn count was reported as Nm 28 having 11% poplar fibers in the total composition. Poplar yarns were investigated for their tensile properties and analyzed under a scanning electron microscope to reveal their morphological features (Fig. 6). The blend ratios and the mechanical performance related to these variants are the focus of on-going studies.

Figure 6 Poplar thread bobbin (a) and SEM image of poplar yarn (b)

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